

INCREASING MENTAL CREATIVITY OF PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS THROUGH STORIES

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ABSTRACT

In an era of increasing globalization, the upbringing of the third generation of the Renaissance is becoming more and more important. It can be overcome by changing the indicators and, above all, in the primary school stage. In other words, there is a need for new, innovative approaches in organizing the educational activities of primary school students to increase the creativity of young people. This article discusses how to increase the mental creativity of primary school students through stories.

One of the main conditions for creating innovations in the education system at this stage is pedagogical design. In our opinion, it is the pedagogical design that allows us to consider various aspects of the development of educational activities of children of primary school age in the most holistic and systematic way, both at the level of organizational conditions and at the level of implementation of educational activities. In this approach, the components of learning activities are carried out by students in part and mainly at the reproductive level. The introduction of advanced pedagogical and new information technologies in education not only increases the effectiveness of teaching, but also plays an important role in cultivating an independent and logical thinking, well-rounded, highly spiritual person through the application of scientific achievements in practice. First of all, all educators turn to books to increase the intellectual thinking and creativity of the younger generation.

Because the child learns to think by reading stories, fairy tales, vocabulary increases, in turn, the worldview is formed and mental creativity develops.

A story is a small work of art that summarizes a specific event in a person's life, important aspects of life. The story often depicts an episode in a person's life. Its content is more vital than in a fairy tale. The story is connected with a certain period. Due to the interest of the heroes in the spirituality of the heroes, they begin to gain a certain understanding of the light and dark aspects of life. Their love of beauty and elegance, their hatred of evil are formed during the acquaintance with and analysis of stories. Story content is a genre suitable for elementary school students. Younger students are more interested in the behavior, appearance, portraiture, and stories of the protagonist's world. Therefore, introducing children to the story is linked to explaining its subject. One of the main types of work is to open

the content of the story read in the explanatory reading lessons dedicated to reading the story in primary school, to work on the dictionary, to retell the read text. When working with students on a story, the teacher has the following opportunities:

1. Opportunity to communicate with the child
2. Ability to transfer knowledge
3. Opportunity to teach life lessons
5. Opportunity to stimulate children's imagination
6. Opportunity to learn the importance of books and reading
7. Opportunity to learn language and vocabulary
8. Ability to increase the child's IQ

After reading the story, its content must be analyzed. Because this process clarifies the realities that the student does not understand, meditates and seeks solutions to existing problems. The content of a story is usually analyzed based on questions. Questionnaires are used for two purposes: to analyze the content of a story and to compare and contrast evidence, reasoning, conclusions, events, and behaviors. It is also important to explain the meaning of the words and phrases that students will understand in the story reading class, otherwise they will not be able to understand the meaning of the story. In reading the story, the analysis of its content and, on this basis, the development of students' speech play a central role. After reading the story, students should be given time to think and prepare to give their feedback. The purpose of the first questions asked about the work is to find out if the children liked the story and which character in it influenced the child. Only then do the subject of the story use

questions that help to reveal the direction of the story, to understand the character of the characters, and finally to know the main idea of the work. In the analysis of a work of art, the types of work, such as the description of the protagonist, the construction of the work and the analysis of the language, should not be neglected, devoting themselves to the full explanation of the subject. The texts of the fairy-tale genre attract the child with their charm. But the story genre is also unique in its vitality. The events in the story develop rapidly. It describes human life, the life scenes associated with it. Students are interested in the character of the protagonist, the features in them. For example, in the 3rd grade "O 'winter book" "Hassa" (Khudoiberdiyev Tokhtaboyev), "Helped" (Yayra Abdullayeva), "Rabbit" (Nosir Fozilov), "Chana" (O. Hoshimov), "Bobonur" (Safar Barnoyev), "Priceless Wealth" (Hakim Nazir) and other interesting stories are given. Because of their interest in the spirituality of the protagonists, they begin to gain a certain understanding of the light and dark aspects of life. In them, a love of beauty and sophistication, a hatred of evil is formed during the acquaintance with and analysis of stories. For example, in the 3rd grade story "Good Virtue", Zarifjon's mother Nazokat tells her sister to return the money she lost from the passenger's cyst, and to tell her son that she will never take anyone's money and will always be honest. Its significance is that it always calls for honesty, not to betray the rights of others, and always to do good. In primary school, various analyzes on the study of the subject, composition, protagonists of the story are carried out on the basis of work on the text. At the same time, the creative

activity of the student increases, the scope of creative thinking expands. The study and analysis of the protagonists of the story "Good Virtue", their behavior, based on the text, can be done on the basis of the following plan:

1. Find out why Aunt Nazokat returned the money.
2. Say what is the best quality in the world.
3. Contemplate honesty.

After that, students think consciously about the story. They draw independent conclusions for the story. The following work is carried out on the basis of the text to master the content of the story:

1. Answer the teacher's questions on the content of the text.
2. Complete a story-based quiz.
3. Have your student ask questions about the content of the story.
4. Draw pictures that match the content of the story.
5. Divide the text of the story into parts.
6. Find a title for each section.
7. Plan the story.
8. Plan-based retelling (full, abbreviated, and creative retelling).
9. Write a statement based on the plan.

The comprehensibility of the text of the story being read is crucial in the analysis. Comprehension means the originality of the artistic world created by the writer, the relevance of the figurative image to the student's life experience, level of

knowledge. When studying a story, questions are usually asked by the teacher, but it is also very helpful to ask students questions about the content of the work, revealing the behavior of the participants. This method is very popular with children and enlivens the work, helps students to better understand the content of the work, the ability to express their thoughts consistently, to fully remember the connection between the content and the events. The following methods should be used in this process:

1. FSMU method (Opinion, reason, example, generalization). Using this method, students learn to express themselves freely, to think consciously.
2. Syncline method. Using this method, students will be able to prove, explain and analyze their ideas.

In conclusion, it should be noted that today young people with strong development in all areas, high intellectual potential are important for the development of our society and the future of our country. In this process, stories play an important role in enriching the mental and spiritual world of the younger generation, developing their worldview. Through stories, children learn to think critically, increase mental creativity. That is why every educator must know how to use stories correctly during lessons and how to analyze them correctly.

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